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Instructional Supervision And Workload As Correlates Of Teachers' Task Performance In Public Secondary Schools In Imo State

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ABSTRACT

The general purpose of the study was to investigate instructional supervision and workload as correlates of teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State. Six research questions guided the study and six hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The correlational research design was adopted for the study. The study was conducted in Imo State. The Population of the study consisted of 510 principals in public secondary schools in Imo State. The sample of the study comprised 255 principals from public secondary schools in Imo State. The study used three major instruments: Instructional Supervision Questionnaire (ISQ), Questionnaire on Teachers Workload (QTW) and Teachers Task Performance Questionnaire (TTPQ). The instruments were subjected to face and construct validation. The instruments reliability were established through a pilot test. The data collected were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha and coefficient values of 0.75, 0.82 and 0.84. Pearson Product Moment Correlational correlation was used to answer the research questions and to test the hypotheses. The finding of the study revealed that classroom observation, evaluation of teachers professional records, professional development of teachers and lesson notes preparation have high positive relationship with teachers task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State. Continuous assessment has a moderate positive relationship with teachers task performance while large class size have high negative relationship with teachers task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State. Based on these findings, the researcher concludes based on the findings of the study that instructional supervision and workload have significant relationship with teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State. Based on these findings and conclusion, the researcher recommended that Principals of secondary schools should conduct regular classroom observations to monitor teachers' instructional practices. It was also recommended that Government at all levels and educational stakeholders should reduce class sizes by recruiting more qualified teachers and constructing additional classrooms.

Keywords: instructional supervision, Teachers Workload, Teachers Task Performance

INTRODUCTION

Education serves as the foundation upon which every society is built. It is the primary tool through which societies cultivate and develop their human capital. The quality of education within a society is intricately linked to the quality of teaching and learning taking place in its schools. The realization of the goals of education is dependent on teacher task performance. A teacher is a person who helps others to acquire knowledge, competences or values. The teacher is the key planner of knowledge and plays a significant

role in nation-building. Therefore, their performance is critical to the realization of school goals. The performance of secondary school teachers significantly affects their institution's effectiveness in preparing qualified students for the future by reinforcing the teaching and learning process, aligning with national goals and curriculum completion. Task performance can be defined as the quantitative and qualitative expression of an individual, a group, a unit, or an organization assigned to do a task's level of achievement of the intended goal, as well as the effort done to reach the specified goal. Teachers task performance is defined as the extent to which teachers' carryout their primary duty of teaching and the extent to which they conduct themselves professionally (Odunayo, 2024). In a similar vein, Koko and Uzoho (2023) defined teachers' task performance as teachers' commitment to their task. Nwite (2016) further elaborated that teachers task performance has to do with the holistic activities of the teacher which involves their judiciousness in lesson preparation, disciplining of their students, evaluating learning outcome, active participation in school activities such as planning school extra-curricular and assisting school administrator. This indicates that teachers' task performance refers to the degree at which teachers discharge their primary duty of teaching and learning, as well their general attitude towards the teaching profession and her activities.

Teachers' task performance in a school setting refers to the duties completed by a teacher over a specific period in the school system in order to achieve the school's goals. Teachers' task performance involves all the activities carried out by the teacher to achieve the desired effects on students. It involves the extent to which the teacher participates in the overall running of the school in order to achieve the expected objective and goals of the school (Nwankwoala, 2020). Teachers' task performance refers to the extent to which teachers are committed to pedagogical delivery and display of moral uprightness and academic excellence in the teaching profession. It is also measured in terms of the quality and standard of outputs being produced. According to Umoru (2018: 14) defined teachers task performance as the ability of teachers in lesson preparation, involvement of co-curricular activities of work, pupil discipline management, counselling and guidance, participating in staff meetings, actual teaching, routine assessment of learners, maintenance of record of work covered and learners' records and time management. In Imo State, public secondary schools are experiencing a growing concern over the poor task performance of teachers, which manifests in inadequate lesson preparation, poor classroom management, lack of instructional delivery, and low student academic outcomes. Despite government efforts in teacher recruitment, training, and provision of teaching resources, many teachers appear to lack motivation, show signs of burnout, or fail to meet expected performance standards. In the context of the study, teachers' task performance is defined as the level to which teachers carryout their expected roles and responsibilities in achieving educational goals. Thus, teachers' task performance is based on their ability to discharge their teaching duties and guide students learning for improved performance. For teachers to achieve optimum performance on the task, there is need to ensure discipline and commitment on the task. Sadly, it appears that the level of teacher task performance in Imo State seem not to be impressive. Poor teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State has become a growing concern, with potential consequences for students' academic achievement and the overall quality of education.

This is evident in cases where teachers appear to neglect duties shown in their lateness to work and partaking in personal businesses during school hours. Reports from Dike (2023) and Nwosu (2020) seem to indicate that some teachers in public secondary schools in Imo State come to school late, leave without permission most times, absent themselves from school with flimsy excuses, fail to have up to date lesson plan and note, many do not cover the curriculum content and teach without proper instructional materials. In the same vein, Ekweogu (2020) reported a sense of indifference and disengagement among secondary school teachers in Imo State, implying a deterioration in their overall task performance. Ekweogu further stated that this negative attitude on the task takes many forms, including poor educational delivery, inefficient classroom management, and decreased student enthusiasm. This situation could be blamed on poor instructional supervisions by principals and teachers' workload (Koko & Uzoho, 2024; Nwankwoala, 2020 & Umaru, 2018). The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) identified management of

curriculum and instruction, supervision of classroom instruction, monitoring and evaluating students' progress and achievement, promoting and enhancing learning environment, establishing and supporting continuous staff development and procuring instructional materials for teaching and learning as major supervisory functions of secondary school principals.

The educational policy also makes it clear that one of the cardinal objectives of administration in education is to ensure quality control through regular and continuous supervision of instruction and other educational services. Principals as instructional leaders, are responsible for the supervision, monitoring, assessment, evaluation and dissemination of current information on academic and current teaching techniques to teachers leading to effective teaching and learning. As school managers, principals are expected to effectively guide and control administrative processes for the purpose of achieving predetermined secondary education objectives as enshrined in the (FRN, 2013). Madudili (2021) opined that principals owe it as a duty to modify the attitude of the staff and motivate them to put in their best at achieving educational goals. The functions of principals among others include delegating of duties, budgeting, instructional supervision, maintenance of physical plants and custodial services to students and staff as well as playing the role of a liaison officer between the school, ministry and the community (Educational Research Service, 2017).

Instructional supervision is a collaborative effort that involves a set of activities designed to improve teaching and learning exercises. The purpose of instructional supervision in secondary schools by principals is not to identify faults or punish teachers; rather, it is meant to work cooperatively with teachers to improve their task performance. It is one of the elements of the administrative process that is concerned with the day-to-day guiding and directing the activities of teachers to enable them to undertake their teaching task successfully. Instructional supervision, which is concerned with learning in the classroom, includes all those activities by educational administrators that may express leadership in the improvement of teaching and learning, such as observation of class instruction, conducting teachers meetings, conducting group and individual conferences and reorganizing curriculum (Mensah et al., 2020). It is seen as the process of ensuring improvements in the teaching and learning through a network of cooperative activities and democratic relationship of persons concerned with teaching and learning to achieve an effective education system. Madudili (2021) defined instructional supervision as a collaborative effort involving a set of activities designed with the objective of bringing improvements in teaching and learning in schools. It is also viewed as all efforts assigned to school officials in providing leadership to teachers and other educational workers to improve instruction, stimulate professional growth and development of teachers, select and revise educational objectives, material of instructions, and methods of teaching, and the evaluation of instruction (Agogbu et al., 2021).

Instructional supervision involves appropriate recognition of teachers' abilities which assists in giving clear direction for their work in the school (Khuninkeeree et al., 2019). Instructional supervision according to Madudili (2015; 3) is a process that focuses on instruction and provides teachers with information about their teaching so as to develop instructional skills to improve performance. Uwaleke et al. (2021) defined instructional supervision as the maximum development of the teacher into the most professionally efficient and effective person he is capable of becoming. In the context of this study, instructional supervision is defined as the art of over-seeing the teaching-learning process, therefore making sure that the school is administered, managed and leads in an effective manner to achieve the educational objectives. Effective instructional supervision is an instrument used in schools for behavior modification. It determines the goals of school and means of accomplishing them. Therefore, instructional supervision in school has been seen as a motivator whereby one person who is the head motivates others towards the achievement of specific goals of the school (Abbas et al., 2022). Umaru (2018) stated that improving instructional supervision in schools through building principals' capacity also add that, even though stakeholders in education may be aware of the value of the principal's instructional supervisory responsibilities, effective instructional supervisory skills are hardly practiced. Dumba et al. (2023) posited that the main instructional supervisory role of school principals include giving teachers direction, resources and supporting them.

Principals through instructional supervision directly determine the teachers' perception of teaching and curriculum instruction as the principal supervises teachers based on the schemes of work, specific objectives of the lesson notes, lesson plan, class attendance, absenteeism and levels of hard work, set induction, class control, students' involvement in the lesson, class work, projects and class exercise, teachers conduct and dressing among others. Madudili (2021) outlined some instructional supervision practices available for principals to help teachers improve on their teaching performance and also to facilitate effective instructional supervision in schools. Some of the practices include classroom observation, evaluation of teachers' professional records and professional development of teachers. Uwaleke et al. (2021) averred that the supervisory practices of the principals include classroom observation, regular checking of lesson plans, staff evaluation, monitoring of weekly implementation, and weekly implementation of the scheme of work among others. Dumba et al (2022) stated that instructional supervision practices include routine inspection, academic appraisal and continuous professional development. The researcher investigated classroom observation, evaluation of teachers' professional records and professional development of teachers.

Classroom observation involves the systematic monitoring of teachers' lesson delivery during the teaching and learning process. Uwaleke et al. (2021) defined classroom observation as the process by which a principal as a supervisor visits classrooms to watch teachers and students in action during the teaching and learning process. Classroom observation is one of the stages of clinical supervision, and its main goal is to capture the reality of the lesson objectively and fully enough to allow the supervisor and teacher to reconstruct the lesson as accurately as possible later on in order to assess it (Madudili, 2021). Teachers may acquire problem-solving skills when visited by principals in classrooms as principals are required to observe the teaching techniques and methods adopted by teachers on regular basis to identify the weaknesses of every teacher and discuss the observations with them promptly and politely to enhance their effective task performance. Dumba et al (2023) stated that classroom observation allows principals to become aware of what is happening in classrooms, assess if sound instruction is being delivered and share and discuss this information with teachers. Principals utilize classroom observation as a means of communication to address a variety of issues that affect learning in specific classrooms (Umaru, 2018). Similarly, principals' checking of teachers' professional records is seen as an instructional supervision technique for improving teachers' task performance.

Principal evaluating teachers' professional records is an important instructional supervision practice in secondary schools. During records observation the principals must be objective, maintain confidentiality and provide feedback to the teacher (Madudili, 2021). Evaluation is the comparison of actual results against the agreed standards. It looks at what a plan set out to achieve, what has been accomplished and how it has been accomplished. Through supervision, teachers could be assessed on how they deliver their lessons. Such an assessment may help principals to easily identify the strengths and weaknesses of every teacher. Principal teachers evaluation refers to the process by which an instructional supervisor assess and rates teachers' performance and effectiveness as they undertake their responsibilities (Uwaleke et al., 2021). The outcome of an evaluation exercise is used to provide feedback to teachers to enhance their professional development. Teacher evaluation involves the appraisal of teaching and learning activities. Among supervisory duties, the principals must check the teaching standards by reference to teachers' professional records (Aseka, 2016). Dumba et al (2023) noted that the instructional role of principals in high performing schools include checking lesson plans, schemes of work, teacher attendance and class registers regularly. During records observation the principal must be objective, maintain confidentiality and provide feedback to the teacher (Hunsaker&Hunsaker, 2019). Aseka (2016) averred that many studies have revealed that most principals focused more on professional records than the real practical work being done by teachers. Uwaleke et al. (2021) opined that principals are expected to check teachers lesson plans, schemes of work, teacher attendance and class registers regularly so as to ensure that teachers carry out their expected roles and responsibilities. In addition to evaluating teachers' professional records, professional development of teachers is another instructional supervision practice that would improve teachers' performance.

Instructional supervision therefore is an essential tool for staff development. According to Glickman et al (2017), a long-term objective of supervision is to develop teachers professionally towards a point where the teachers, coached by supervisors, can take complete charge of instructional enhancement. Professional development of teachers are important aspects of education process that deal with the art of acquiring skills in the teaching profession (Igwegbe, 2021). They are essential practices that enhance subject mastery, teaching methodology and classroom management. Madumere-Obike in Igwegbe, (2021) stated that the objective of staff development is that it ensures the promotion of professional growth, helps to improve pedagogical skills, keeps teachers abreast with new knowledge and meets particular needs, such as curriculum development and orientation. Other objectives are that it helps in fostering leadership responsibility, helps new teachers to adjust to teaching field, helps to promote mutual respect among teachers and recognizes the need for modern teaching methods. Through effective professional development programmes like organizing workshops, sponsoring teachers' participation in higher education courses and encouraging mentorship programmes, principals can increase teachers' capacity and abilities on the task (Dumba et al, 2023). This means that a well-planned and administered staff development programme may be one of the most critical factors for improving teachers' task performance in secondary schools. However, the teachers task performance could be determined by teachers' workload. Workload is the totality of teaching and non-teaching responsibilities assigned to a teacher, as his contribution to the achievement to the overall educational goal and objective. Workload can be seen as the amount of work or of working time expected or assigned (Weba, 2020). Koko and Uzoho (2023) defined workload as the totality of teaching and non-teaching tasks assigned to a teacher for the attainment of the overall educational objectives in the school. In the context of the present study, the research defines workload as the total amount of work, including tasks, responsibilities, and activities that a teacher is expected to perform in a given period of time. It can refer to the quantity and complexity of work in a task, as well as the amount of time and effort required to complete it.

The components of workload include planning and writing of lesson notes, lesson delivery, filling out diaries, marking of registers, class management/control, evaluation and recording of test, assignments and examination outcomes (Oluwale, 2018). According to Koko and Uzoho (2023; 23), some factors that contribute to teachers' workload as found in literature include class size, number of subjects' teachers teaching, writing and preparation of lesson notes, responding to students' complaints, engaging in extra-curriculum activities, marking and computation of students' continuous assessment scores. For the present study the researcher focused on large class size, continuous assessment and lesson notes preparation as components of workload.

Class size refers to the number of students in a given course or classroom, specifically either the number of students being taught by individual teachers in a course or classroom or the average number of students being taught by teachers in a school or educational system (Ayeni, 2016). The term may also be the number of students participating in learning experience. Class size is almost an administrative decision over which teachers have little or no control. Atodo (2018) defined class size as an educational tool that can be used to describe the average number of students per class in a school. Odeyale et al. (2018) stated that countries like Australia, Canada, Romania, Czech Republic, United States of America and Slovenia have less than 30 students recommended for a standard class and countries like Norway, Turkey and Netherlands recommended 20 or less than 20 students for a standard class while Japan and Singapore have above 30 students recommended for a standard class. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) in Odeyale et al puts student- teacher ratio in secondary schools at 42 as of 2004 and puts it at 31 as of 2010 while its lowest value was 25 in the year 2008. The recommended class size for secondary schools in Nigeria is a maximum of 40 students per class. This guideline is supported by the National Policy on Education, which aims to promote effective teaching and learning environments (FRN, 2013). Additionally, the All Nigerian Conference of Principals of Secondary Schools (ANCOPSS) also endorses this maximum class size of 40 in secondary schools in Nigeria to facilitate better educational outcomes (Dang, 2022). Therefore, in this study, class size with 1 - 40 students per teacher will be regarded as small or standard class size while class size with 41 and above

students per teacher will be considered as large class size. Large classes present more challenges for classroom management, students' control, and marking, planning, and assessment (Atodo, 2018). Teachers are put under more strain when faced with large classes. Hodges in Atodo (2018) stated that some of the effects of large class size include passive attitude of students, alienation of some students especially slow learners and the negative perception of lessons conducted in overcrowded classes. Similar to large class size, continuous assessment is another component of workload.

Continuous assessment, often referred to as formative assessment, has become a prevalent practice in educational settings globally. This approach involves the ongoing evaluation of students' progress and understanding throughout a course, providing valuable insights for both educators and learners (Brown et al., 2022). However, the implementation of continuous assessment poses challenges for teachers, significantly impacting their workload. As Uwalaka (2015) noted, teachers find themselves continuously engaged in evaluating and providing feedback on students' work, demanding a considerable amount of time and effort. The nature of continuous assessment requires frequent monitoring and assessment, leading to an increased burden on teachers' schedules. The demands of continuous assessment can contribute to stress and burnout among educators. Ludars et al. (2018) suggests that the constant need for assessment and feedback can overwhelm teachers, affecting their overall well-being. Juggling multiple assessments and keeping up with timely and meaningful feedback requires significant organizational skills and time investment, potentially leading to exhaustion. Jones and Smith (2021) stated that the emotional and mental toll on teachers may have repercussions on the quality of education they provide and their long-term commitment to the profession. The accountability and reporting requirements associated with continuous assessment add another layer of complexity for teachers. As education systems emphasize data-driven decision-making, teachers are often required to compile and analyze assessment data to meet administrative demands (Taylor, 2020). This additional administrative burden can detract from the time and energy teachers allocate to actual teaching and engaging with students. Striking a balance between fulfilling administrative responsibilities and providing effective continuous assessment can be a considerable challenge for educators. Just like continuous assessment, lesson notes preparation is another component of workload.

Lesson notes are informal and personalized records of teachers' reflections and direction after delivering a lesson. Ikegbusi (2019) stated that lesson notes serve as a reflective document that teachers create after delivering a lesson. It captures the essence of the lesson, including its flow, the students' engagement, and the overall effectiveness of the teaching strategies employed. While lesson plans are formal documents prepared in advance to outline the objectives, materials, and methods for a lesson, lesson notes are more informal and personal, focusing on the teacher's reflections and assessments of the lesson's impact on students (Brown & Taylor, 2020). Preparing lesson notes is an integral part of a teacher's workload, as it not only contributes to personal professional development but also enhances the overall teaching process. Lesson notes serve as a record of what transpired in the classroom, providing accountability for teachers (Ikegbusi, 2019). This documentation can be useful for evaluations, discussions with colleagues, or meetings with parents regarding student progress. The increasing emphasis on differentiated instruction and personalized learning further contributes to the complexity of lesson note preparation (Johnson, 2018). Teachers are tasked with tailoring their lessons to accommodate diverse learning styles and individual student needs. These factors may be contribution to seemly poor teachers task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State.

This is because field observation by the researcher and interactions with some parents who are members of the Parents Teachers Association (PTA) seem to indicate that parents are not impressed with the performance of some teachers in public secondary schools in Imo State. Some parents complained about the failure of teachers to give their children assignment and homeworks that will keep them engaged at home. Some parents even complained about how scanty their children's notes which is as a result of the failure of some teachers to provide less notes for students. Interactions with some principals also corroborate the claims by the parents. Some principals decry the failure of some teachers to provide up-to-date lesson notes. Further observation by the researcher seems to show that some secondary school

teachers are seen conducting other businesses in public markets and shopping centres during school hours. The researcher is worried that if this unfortunate situation is not curbed it will eventually lead to poor students' academic performance. It is against this background that the researcher investigated instructional supervision and workload as correlates of teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State.

Statement of the Problem

Teachers are vital stakeholders in educational development, serving as the backbone of any successful education system. The government of Imo State has consistently emphasized the critical role of teachers in achieving quality secondary education within the state. However, despite this emphasis, there seems to be a noticeable gap between the expected standards of instructional delivery and the actual quality of educational service delivery in public secondary schools. It appears that in some public secondary schools in Imo State, there is seem to be growing lack of commitment among some teachers to effectively discharge their duties. This concern is reflected by the researcher's field observation which revealed that in some schools, the staff rooms and even classrooms have been transformed into makeshift shopping centres, with some teachers engaging in the sale of various products to both colleagues and students. Furthermore, the researcher observed that in some public secondary schools, the burden of teaching has been disproportionately shifted from more experienced and older teachers to younger teachers and, in many cases, youth corp members. This situation often results in senior teachers transferring their responsibilities to younger colleagues, overwhelming them with excessive duties which seem to increase their workload. This pattern raises questions about the effectiveness of principals in fulfilling their instructional supervisory roles. The researcher is worried that if this unfortunate situation is not curbed it will eventually lead to students' poor academic achievement which will affect the quality of human capital and work force in Imo State in particular and Nigeria in general. Hence, the study seeks to determine if these issues are as a result of poor instructional supervision and workload. The researcher is deeply concerned that these issues could significantly impact teachers' task performance. It is against this backdrop that the researcher investigated whether there is a correlation between instructional supervision, workload and teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of the study was to investigate instructional supervision and workload as correlates of teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. examine relationship between classroom observation and teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State
2. determine relationship between evaluation of teachers professional records and teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between classroom observation and teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State?
2. What is the relationship between evaluation of teachers' professional records and teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Classroom observation has no significant relationship with teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State.
2. Evaluation of teachers' professional records has no significant relationship with teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State.

METHOD

The study adopted the correlational research design. The correlational research design examined the degree, patterns and strength of relationship between two or more variables being studied rather than explore causal relationship between them. Thus, the correlational research design provides clues for the proper understanding of patterns of relationships among variables in the study. Therefore, the correlational research design was considered appropriate for the study because the study was a correlational study that sought to establish the magnitude and level of relationship between instructional supervision and workload as correlates of teachers’ task performance in public secondary in Imo State. The researcher believed that good supervision and moderate workload would help in curbing the problem of poor job performance in these schools. The population of the study comprised 510 principals in all public secondary schools in the six (6) Education Zones of Imo State. This number was based on data from Post Primary School Service Commission (PPSSC) Headquarters Owerri, as at July, 2024. Only principals in the state government owned secondary schools were used for the study. The sample of the study comprised 255 principals from public secondary schools in Imo State. The sample size was determined using the simple random sampling technique. Specifically, the researcher employed simple random sampling to select 50% of the study population. The study employed three major instruments: Instructional Supervision Questionnaire (ISQ), Questionnaire on Teachers Workload (QTW) and Teachers Task Performance Questionnaire (TTPQ). The instruments were subject to face and construct validity and experts to determined the face and construct validity of the questionnaires by vetting the items in terms of clarity of the words used, whether the items are easily understandable, relevance of items to the subject matter and content coverage of the questionnaire. The instruments reliability were established through Cronbach Alpha and coefficient values of 0.75, 0.82 and 0.84. The researcher administered 255 copies of questionnaires were administered by the researcher and the research assistants in the respective classrooms of the respondents. The completed questionnaires were retrieved on the spot to minimize attrition. Research questions 1-6 were answered using Pearson Product Moment Correlational correlation. The statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 26 was used for the analysis. The decision rule was based on the following guidelines Price et al (2017) provided:

RESULT

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between classroom observation and teachers’ task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State?*

Table 1: Summary of Pearson Correlation Analysis between Classroom Observation and Teachers’ Task Performance in public secondary schools in Imo State

		Classroom Observation	Teachers’ Task Performance	Remark
Classroom Observation	Pearson Correlation	1	0.721**	High Positive relationship
	Sig, (2-tailed)		0.000	
	N	238	238	
Teachers’ Task Performance	Pearson Correlation	0.721**	1	
	Sig, (2-tailed)	0.000		
	N	238	238	

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Data in Table 1 reveals that the Pearson’s Correlation Coefficient is $r=0.721$. This shows that a high

positive relationship exists between classroom observation and teachers task performance. This implies that if principals regularly conduct classroom observation in their schools it would improve teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State. Thus, there is a high positive relationship between classroom observation and teachers task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between evaluation of teachers' professional records and teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State?*

Table 2: Summary of Pearson Correlation Analysis between Evaluation of Teachers' Professional Records and Teachers' Task Performance in public secondary schools in Imo State

		Evaluation of Teachers' Professional Records	Teachers' Task Performance	Remark
Evaluation of Teachers' Professional Records	Pearson Correlation	1	0.706**	High Positive relationship
	Sig, (2-tailed)		0.000	
Teachers' Task Performance	N	238	238	
	Pearson Correlation	0.706**	1	
	Sig, (2-tailed)	0.000		
	N	238	238	

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Data in Table 2 reveals that the Pearson's Correlation Coefficient is $r=0.706$. This shows that a high positive relationship exists between evaluation of teachers' professional records and teachers' task performance. This implies that if principals evaluation of teachers' professional records in their schools it would improve teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State. Thus, there is a high positive relationship between evaluation of teachers' professional records and teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Classroom observation has no significant relationship with teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State.

Table 3: Test of Significance of Pearson Correlation on the Relationship between Classroom Observation and Teachers' Task Performance in public secondary schools in Imo State

		Correlation		
		Classroom Observation	Teachers' Task Performance	Remark
Classroom Observation	Pearson Correlation	1	0.721 ^{**}	Significant
	Sig, (2-tailed)		0.000	
	N	238	238	
Teachers' Task Performance	Pearson Correlation	0.721 ^{**}	1	
	Sig, (2-tailed)	0.000		
	N	238	238	

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Data presented on Table 3 indicates the correlation coefficient (r) as 0.721 with a p-value = 0.000. Since the P value of 0.000 was less than .05 (P<.05), it means that effect of classroom observation on teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State is statistically significant. This means that there is a significant relationship between classroom observation and teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Hypothesis 2: Evaluation of teachers' professional records has no significant relationship with teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State.

Table 4: Test of Significance of Pearson Correlation on the Relationship between Evaluation of Teachers' Professional Records and Teachers' Task Performance in public secondary schools in Imo State

		Correlation		
		Evaluation of Teachers' Professional Records	Teachers' Task Performance	Remark
Evaluation of Teachers' Professional Records	Pearson Correlation	1	0.706 ^{**}	Significant
	Sig, (2-tailed)		0.000	
	N	238	238	
Teachers' Task Performance	Pearson Correlation	0.706 ^{**}	1	
	Sig, (2-tailed)	0.000		
	N	238	238	

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Data presented on Table 9 indicates the correlation coefficient (r) as 0.706 with a p -value = 0.000. Since the P value of 0.000 was less than .05 ($P < .05$), it means that effect evaluation of teachers' professional records on teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State is statistically significant. This means that there is a significant relationship between evaluation of teachers' professional records and teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Summary of Findings

Findings of the study are summarized as follows:

1. There is a high positive relationship between classroom observation and teachers task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State. Furthermore, there is a significant relationship between classroom observation and teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State.
2. There is a high positive relationship between evaluation of teachers' professional records and teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State. Furthermore, there is a significant relationship between evaluation of teachers' professional records and teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State.

CONCLUSION

The researcher concluded based on the findings of the study that instructional supervision and workload have significant relationship with teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State. The study showed that classroom observation, evaluation of teachers professional records, professional development of teachers and lesson notes preparation have high positive relationship with teachers task performance in public secondary schools in Imo State. It is therefore imperative that measures are put in place to improve instructional supervision practices and better manage workloads in public secondary schools in Imo State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher proffered the following recommendations:

1. Principals of secondary schools should conduct regular classroom observations to monitor teachers' instructional practices. Constructive feedback and professional support should be provided to help teachers improve their teaching effectiveness.
2. Principals and other administrators of secondary schools should institute a routine evaluation of teachers' professional records, including lesson plans, attendance registers, and student performance records. Training on effective record-keeping practices should be provided to teachers.

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